

Urgent Public Health Need Site

Policies, Procedures, & Protocols Manual

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Land Acknowledgement

We would like to acknowledge that these policies and procedures were created in Mi'kma'ki, the ancestral and unceded territory of the Mi'kmaq people. This territory is covered by the "Treaties of Peace and Friendship" which Mi'kmaq and Wolastoqyik (Woo-last-two-wi-ik) signed with the British Crown in 1725. The Treaties did not deal with the surrender of lands and resources but in fact recognized Mi'kmaq and Wolastoqyik title and established the rules for what was to be an ongoing relationship between nations. Every individual and every institution has a role to play in making the needed changes to dismantle systemic racism and oppression against Black and Indigenous People in Canada. We think one action that anyone can take is raising your own cultural awareness - learning about other cultures, asking questions, reading, and becoming more self-aware. Through this acknowledgment, and the harm reduction philosophy, we commit ourselves to this lifelong work in creating effective change within our society. Honoring this treaty relationship through a land acknowledgment is just one of the many steps that can be taken towards reconciliation as outlined in the 94 calls to action issued by the Truth and Reconciliation Commission of Canada in 2015.

The Urgent Public Health Need Site (UPHNS) Community of Practice would like to acknowledge all the following groups: The HaliFIX Overdose Prevention Society Executive Committee as well as the larger supporters and members for their support in implementing Atlantic Canada's first overdose prevention site, The Mi'kmaq Native Friendship Centre, Mainline Needle Exchange, Dalhousie Schulich School of Law and Dr. Peter AIDS Foundation.

The development of this document would have never been possible without countless hours of dedicated volunteers trying to advance drug policy in Atlantic Canada and for that, we thank you.

Disclaimer

These policies and procedures were developed for a very conservative and unsupportive government, and it reflects in some of the policies and procedures. This document is meant to guide overdose prevention sites or safe consumption sites, it is not meant to be exactly replicated as it stands. The following is meant to be a tool kit to start planning policy and procedures for your own organization.

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1. Definitions

- 1) "Exemption" refers to the Exemption issued to the UPHNS Overdose Prevention Society by Health Canada pursuant to Subsection 56(1) of the Controlled Drugs and Substances Act to operate an Overdose Prevention Site.
- 2) "UPHNS Overdose Prevention Society" refers to the organization that was granted the Exemption to operate an Overdose Prevention Society.
- 3) "Harm Reduction" refers to a set of practical strategies and ideas aimed at reducing negative consequences associated with substance use.
- 4) "Harassment" refers to physical or verbal behaviour or intimidation that offends or humiliates another individual and includes discrimination related to, but not limited to, an individual's race, religious beliefs, colour, gender, physical disability, mental disability, marital status, sex, age, sexual orientation, civil status, political convictions, language, ancestry, place of origin, family status, source of income, or conviction for an offence for which a pardon has been granted or in respect of which a record suspension has been ordered.
- 5) "Overdose Prevention Site" (OPS) refers to the location where services are provided by the Service Providers to the Service Users within the Service Area.
- 6) "Person in Charge" (PIC) refers to the individual(s) designated by the UPHNS Overdose Prevention Society as responsible for the daily operation of the OPS.
- 7) "Service Area" refers to the location at civic address 123 Drug Using Street where the UPHNS Overdose Prevention Society is permitted to operate an OPS pursuant to the Exemption.
- 8) "Service Provider" refers to an individual working or volunteering at the OPS to provide services to Service Users and includes the PIC.
- 9) "Service Refusal" refers to a circumstance when a Service User is prohibited or banned from accessing the OPS by the PIC.
- 10) "Service User" refers to an individual who is assessed by the Service Providers and provided access to the OPS for the purpose of receiving services, including injection, intranasal, and oral substance consumption.
- 11) "Youth" refers to an individual between the ages of 16-19.

2. Abbreviations

- 1) OPS – Overdose Prevention Site
- 2) PIC – Person in Charge
- 3) IDU – Injection Drug Use

3. Purpose

This document outlines the principles, protocols, training and related supplies required to enable Service Providers to provide low-barrier access to services to Service Users in the OPS. Harm reduction is the main principle that structures these Policies & Procedures.

4. Core Services

The core services of the OPS include:

- (a) The provision of a designated monitored space for substance use;
- (b) The intervention for overdoses;
- (c) Harm reduction teaching, training, and referral services;

- (d) The provision of harm reduction supplies; and
- (e) Direct linkages and referrals to primary care and psychosocial support.

5. Training of Services Providers

- 1) The PIC is responsible to ensure that Service Providers are trained to carry out the responsible provision of services at the OPS.
- 2) All Service Providers must receive training in each of the following:
 - (a) Overdose response;
 - (b) Basic first aid;
 - (c) Naloxone administration;
 - (d) Addiction treatment and ancillary support services available in the community;
 - (e) Client referral to primary care and treatment supports;
 - (f) Confidentiality, including the topics of data collection and client information;
 - (g) Anti-harassment;
 - (h) The Codes of Conduct;
 - (i) De-escalation techniques; and
 - (j) Equipment disposal and transportation of sharps.

6. Position of Trust

Service Providers are in a position of trust to Service Users, many of whom are marginalized and stigmatized. In the course of their duties, Service Providers must always consider and prioritize the interests of Service Users.

7. Fitness to Provide Services

- In order to carry out the responsible provision of services at the OPS, Service Providers must:
- (a) Use sensitivity when providing services to Service Users;
 - (b) Focus on the needs of Service Users;
 - (c) Respectfully engage with Service Users and Service Providers;
 - (d) Analyze each situation with clarity prior to making decisions; and
 - (e) Be capable of discharging their responsibilities:
 - i. Service Providers must engage with other Service Providers on what is safety sensitive work around one's own personal substance consumption. Ideally Service Providers would not show up in any condition which would negatively affect their ability to fulfill their duties.
 - ii. Service Providers have a duty to report to the PIC if there is a substantial question about their own or another Service Provider's ability to fulfill their duties.

8. Consequences of Alleged Misconduct by Service Providers

Any breach of these Policies & Procedures, the Code of Conduct, or an abuse of trust will be investigated by the PIC & the local PWUD advisory committee, to determine what action, if any, should be taken to protect the interests of Service Users and the integrity and reputation of the OPS.

9. Harassment

Service Providers must adhere to the Anti-harassment Policy (**Appendix A**). Harassment will not be tolerated at the OPS. Harassment complaints received must be investigated immediately by the PIC or the UPHNS Overdose Prevention Society in accordance with the Anti-harassment Policy.

10. Confidentiality

- 1) The UPHNS Overdose Prevention Society and the OPS are not custodians as defined in the *Personal Health Informed Act (PHIA)*, however, it recognizes that the protocols set out in *PHIA* demonstrate a best practice guide for the collection, retention, use, and disclosure of Service Users' personal information, including but not limited to health information, and therefore uses *PHIA* as a guide for how to optimally uphold confidentiality.
- 2) Any personal information that is obtained by Service Providers in the course of their duties, including information that is discussed on site, in staff meetings, during debriefings, or in communication systems, must remain confidential.
- 3) All Service Providers must sign the Service Provider Confidentiality Agreement (**Appendix B**), which will continue to bind Service Providers after the completion of their position at the OPS.
- 4) Service Providers must take reasonable precautions to ensure that discussions with Service Users remain as confidential as possible.
- 5) The *Children and Family Services Act* and other statutes may supersede Service User confidentiality, including in the following circumstances:
- 6) Service providers must adhere to the duty to report in accordance with Sections 22-25 of the *Children and Family Services Act*.
- 7) If a Service Provider has information indicating that a child is in need of protective services, they must report that information to an agency.
- 8) The duty to report applies even if the information on which the Service Provider's belief is based on is confidential.
- 9) Relevant information about Service Users may be disclosed outside the OPS in the following circumstances:
 - (a) An emergency requiring the assistance of Emergency Health Services;
 - (b) An emergency in the Service Area requiring the assistance of the police; and/or
 - (c) Statistical information may be shared with the Minister of Health, in accordance with the Exemption, the Nova Scotia Department of Health and Wellness (NSDHW) and Nova Scotia Health Authority.
- 10) Subject to 10(6)(c), Service Users' names will remain confidential and will not be included in the statistical information provided.

11. Documentation and Data Collection

- 1) Service Providers may collect documentation and data to:
 - (a) Evaluate the impact and effectiveness of the program;
 - (b) Address community concerns; and/or
 - (c) To meet regulatory standards for documentation and professional accountability.

12. Codes of Conduct

- 1) The Code of Conduct for the OPS (**Appendix C**) must be posted in the OPS where it is clearly visible to all individuals.

13. Physical Space

- 1) Service Providers must adhere to the following best practices in order to ensure a safer physical space for substance consumption services:
 - (a) Ensure that the space is warm and well-lit so that Service Users can easily use substances;
 - (b) Mirrors must be strategically placed to facilitate monitoring;
 - (c) Provide portable mirrors to Service Users upon request;
 - (d) The disposal systems for both biohazardous waste and sharps must be easily accessible in order to encourage Service Users to dispose of their own equipment;
 - (e) All tables must be made of non-permeable and non-flammable material which can be easily cleaned with hospital grade cleaning supplies;
 - (f) Chairs must be positioned facing a wall to allow the client privacy, but must also be accessible and capable of being periodically monitored;
 - (g) Ensure that there is adequate space to always perform naloxone administration and artificial respiration;
 - (h) Ensure that the pathway to the entrance/exit always remains clear and open in case of emergencies; and
 - (i) Ensure that there is a phone on the premises.

14. OPS Access and Security

- 1) The following precautionary measures will be in place to control the entry to and exit out of the OPS:
 - (a) Service Users will only be provided entry to and exit from the OPS through two sets of exterior doors in the Service Area.
 - (b) Only the PIC and Service Providers who are employed at the OPS will have key access to the OPS during the hours of operation.
 - (c) Only the PIC will have the code to the alarm for the OPS, which is connected to the main building's alarm system.
 - (d) Only the PIC will have access to the box safe which contains any substances left behind at the OPS.
 - (e) Service Providers will have access to mobile alarm lanyards at the OPS, which will connect them to a contracted security company in the event of an emergency.

15. Registration of Service Users

- 1) Service Providers must ensure that service users fill out the User Agreement, Release and Consent form (**Appendix D**) upon their first visit to the OPS prior to receiving services. If a Service User is unable to complete the User Agreement, Release and Consent Form, a Service Provider must assist them with the form.
- 2) Service Users must provide a name and their date of birth on User Agreement, Release and Consent form. The Service Users may choose or be assigned a unique identifier upon registration, which will be used for subsequent visit registrations.
- 3) To maintain low-barrier service provision, any personal information of Service Users that is not included in the User Agreement, Release and Consent form is not required for access to the OPS.
- 4) Service Providers must complete the Daily Statistics Sheet (**Appendix I**) every time a Service User visits the OPS.

16. OPS Eligibility

- 1) A service provider must greet each individual seeking access to the OPS and assess the individual for eligibility.
- 2) For Service Users to be eligible for access to the OPS, they must:
 - (a) Sign and complete the User Agreement, Release and Consent Form;
 - (b) Not be subject to a Service Refusal; and
 - (c) Be 16 years of age or older.
- 3) To ensure the safety of all individuals in the OPS, the PIC has the authority to refuse entry to ineligible individuals and to request them to leave the Service Area

17. Service Users with Special Circumstances

- 1) The PIC must assess and register Service Users with Special Circumstances that are seeking access to the OPS. The following individuals are considered Service Users with Special Circumstances:
 - (a) Youth;
 - (b) Overly Intoxicated Individuals;
 - (c) Pregnant individuals;
 - (d) First-time substance users; and
 - (e) Individuals who do not self-inject.

18. Youth

- 1) A Youth Registration and Assessment intake form (**Appendix F**) must be completed by the PIC for every Youth that seeks access to the OPS.
- 2) Upon a Youth's request to access the OPS, the PIC must perform the following assessment protocol:
 - (a) Determine whether the Youth has a history of IDU and has previously obtained injectable substances with the intention of self-use;
 - (b) If the Youth has not previously used injection drugs, determine whether the Youth intends to use substances if they are denied access to the OPS; and
 - (c) Determine whether the Youth understands the harms associated with substance use, even when using an OPS.
- 3) In determining whether the Youth will be granted access to the OPS, the PIC must consider:
 - (a) That Youth represent the highest risk for acquiring Hepatitis C and HIV through IDU;
 - (b) That Youth presenting to the OPS is an opportune point of contact and that connecting the Youth to the services that they need, based on individual circumstances, is the highest priority; and
 - (c) That refusing Youth entry from the OPS has the potential to create more harm than building relationships and connection.
- 4) The PIC may only grant the Youth access to the OPS for the first time if the Youth shows obvious signs of IDU or when it is expected that they will use substances even if denied access to OPS.
- 5) Once a Youth has been granted access to the OPS by the PIC, Service Providers must offer appropriate referrals to harm reduction and social services.

19. Overly Intoxicated Individuals

- 1) Upon an overly intoxicated individual's request to access the OPS, the PIC must assess for signs and symptoms of existing intoxication that may preclude the Service User's ability to complete registration procedures or to safely consume substances. Definition of an overly intoxicated individual is handled on a case-by-case basis, wherein the individual will be assessed for Level of Consciousness (LOC)/level of sedation, respiratory rate, orientation, and other physical indicators as they may present.
- 2) The PIC may only grant an overly intoxicated individual access to the OPS if they expect that the overly intoxicated individual will use substances even if they are denied access to the OPS.
- 3) Once a Service User is identified as an overly intoxicated individual and is admitted to the OPS to consume a controlled substance pursuant to (1), Service Providers must:
 - (a) Provide the Service User with extra support;
 - (b) Provide the Service User with information about the risks associated with substance mixing and IDU while intoxicated;
 - (c) Provide the Service User with information about harm reduction strategies;
 - (d) Encourage the Service User to postpone using substances until they are no longer at high risk of substance induced toxicity or overdose;
 - (e) Closely monitor the Service User throughout their visit;
 - (f) Advise the Service User to use a smaller dose than usual; and
 - (g) Encourage the Service User to wait in the post injection space for an extended period after they are provided services.
- 4) Service Providers must provide feedback to a Service User who was previously identified as an overly intoxicated individual at a subsequent entry to the OPS, if they return, and remind the Service User of the risks associated with substance use while intoxicated.

20. Pregnant Individuals

- 1) Service Providers must make all reasonable attempts to discreetly and respectfully identify pregnant individuals prior to registration and assessment.
- 2) If a pregnant individual is identified prior to being provided services at the OPS, the PIC must complete the assessment and registration.
- 3) In determining whether the pregnant individual will be provided access to the OPS, the PIC must consider:
 - (a) That pregnant individuals who use substances are less likely to access health care services because of the stigma attached to substance use during pregnancy; and
 - (b) When pregnant individuals present to the OPS, it is an opportunity to develop relationships, to build their trust, and to connect them with health care services.
- 4) Access to the OPS may be granted to a pregnant individual following the assessment by the PIC.
- 5) Once a pregnant individual is identified and granted access to the OPS, Service Providers must:
 - (a) Provide the Service User with information about risks associated with substance use during pregnancy;
 - (b) Engage in discussion with the Service User about their substance use patterns and Harm Reduction strategies; and
 - (c) Offer appropriate referrals to harm reduction and social services.

21. First-time Injectors

- 1) Upon identification of a first-time injector, the PIC must complete the registration and an assessment of the individual. In determining whether the first-time injector will be provided access to the OPS, the PIC must:
 - (a) Balance the harm associated with preventing initiation into IDU with the harm associated with denying first-time injectors with OPS services; and
 - (b) Assess whether the first-time injector intends to use injection drugs if they are denied access to the OPS.
- 2) Once a first-time injector is identified and granted access to the OPS by the PIC, Service Providers must:
 - (a) Provide the Service User with information and counseling about the risks associated with IDU, alternate methods of drug use, and safer injection practices;
 - (b) Engage in a discussion with them about their substance use history and patterns, their harm reduction strategies, and their decision to initiate into IDU; and
 - (c) Offer appropriate referrals to harm reduction, clinical, and social services.

22. Individuals Who are Unable to Self-Inject

- 1) Upon identification of an individual who is unable to self-inject, the RPIC must complete the registration and an assessment of the individual.
- 2) In determining whether the individual who is unable to self-inject will be provided access to the OPS, the PIC must consider:
 - (a) The reason that the individual is unable to self-inject;
 - (b) Whether the individual would be able to self-inject safely with training and education provided by a Service Provider;
 - (c) Whether the individual would be able to self-inject safely with the assistance of any physical supports available at the OPS;
 - (d) That individuals who are unable to self-inject have a significantly heightened risk for Hepatitis C and HIV infection; and
 - (e) The vulnerability of the individual who is unable to self-inject.
- 3) Subject to (2) and in accordance with the Exemption, in cases where the PIC determines that self-injection is not possible, or cannot be performed safely, the PIC may allow an individual accompanying the individual who is unable to self-inject to assist them with the injection if:
 - (a) Both individuals agree to arrangement;
 - (b) The assistance is not in exchange for financial compensation, goods, or services;
 - (c) The provision, administration, or transfer of the controlled substance is not in exchange for financial compensation, goods, or services;
 - (d) The transfer of the controlled substance is only for the purposes of performing the injection on the individual who is unable to self-inject; and
 - (e) Both individuals are informed of the legalities of their decision.
- 4) If an individual who is unable to self-inject has another individual perform the injection, the Service Providers must offer safer injection education to the individual assisting with the injection.

23. Service Refusal

- 1) The PIC has the discretion to refuse services to a Service User. Service User may be subject to a Service Refusal when:
 - (a) They have no intention of using substances on the premises;
 - (b) The OPS is at capacity;

- (c) They have breached the Code of Conduct; and/or
- (d) Admission would endanger the health or safety of anyone at the OPS.
- 2) In making the decision to issue a Service Refusal to a Service User, the PIC must consider:
 - (a) The risk to the Service User;
 - (b) That a Service Refusal should only be implemented as a last resort; and
 - (c) That a Service Refusal should normally be specific and temporary.
- 3) A Service Refusal should represent a proportional response to the offending behaviour or situation and should be employed using the least restrictive means possible.
- 4) The PIC must fill out an Incident Report form (**Appendix H**) after issuing a Service Refusal.

24. Injection Services Protocol

- 1) Prior to a Service User accessing injection services at the OPS, a Service Provider must:
 - (a) Assess the Service User's ability to follow simple directions;
 - (b) Assess the Service User's motor control; and
 - (c) Consider the Service User's state of mind.
- 2) Service Providers may educate Service Users on how to safely prepare, properly inject, and discard syringes in order to minimize the risk of needle stick injury and other harms.
- 3) A Service Provider may not physically assist a Service User to inject substances into their body under any circumstances.
- 4) Service Providers may provide the following equipment to the Service User prior to another Service User proceeding to an injection booth, on an as-needed basis:
 - (a) Tourniquet;
 - (b) Syringe(s);
 - (c) Sterile water;
 - (d) Sterile Cooker;
 - (e) Filters;
 - (f) Alcohol swabs;
 - (g) Tea-light candles;
 - (h) Band-Aids;
 - (i) Ascorbic Acid; and
 - (j) Cleaning supplies.
- 5) In order to ensure that each booth is sterilized following use and prior to use by another Service User, Service Providers must:
 - (a) Assess the injection booth for safety;
 - (b) Request that Service Users dispose of their used needles in a sharps container after their injection and, where possible, supervise the disposal;
 - (c) Request that Service Users not bend or break needles before disposal;
 - (d) Encourage Service Users to clean any debris off of the booth that they were using;
 - (e) Request that the Service User place the injection equipment on the table;
 - (f) Offer hand sanitizer or the option to wash their hands before and after injection; and
 - (g) Ensure that the sharps container is in a safe and accessible area in relation to where the Service User and Service Provider are located.

25. Assistance by Service Providers

- 1) A Service Provider may only provide assistance to Service Users that is within the scope of their training. A Service Provider may:
 - (a) Verbally explain all steps in a safer injection process;

- (b) Palpate a Service User's arms for veins, upon request;
- (c) Identify potential injection sites, including physically guiding a Service User's hand to the appropriate injection area upon request;
- (d) Encourage hand washing as a measure to prevent infection;
- (e) Swab injection site with an alcohol swab to reduce the chance of an infection;
- (f) Tie off the Service User's arm, upon request;
- (g) Physically demonstrate all steps in safer injection process using a separate set of clean equipment and their own body; and/or
- (h) Provide information and guidance on safer jugular self-injection practices, upon request.

26. Managing Specific Behaviours

- 1) Service Providers must consider Harm Reduction principles when managing the behaviours that a Service User may be exhibiting as a result of substance use.
- 2) In managing a Service User's behaviours that are related to substance use, Service Providers must:
 - (a) Attempt to de-escalate the behaviour or the situation in a caring and respectful manner; and
 - (b) Attempt to provide the Service User with access to a safe space once the behaviour or situation has been de-escalated.
- 3) A Service Provider must complete an Incident Report form (**Appendix H**) if any person engages in harassing, violent, or threatening behaviour or if a person otherwise breaches the Code of Conduct.

27. Injuries and Exposure to Blood and Bodily Fluids

- 1) In the event of a needle stick injury, Service Providers must instruct the injured individual to cleanse the area of the puncture site thoroughly with warm water and soap, or a suitable antiseptic.
- 2) In the event of an eye splash, Service Providers must instruct the injured individual to flush the eye with tap water for 10-15 minutes.
- 3) In the event of a needle stick injury or an eye splash, Service Providers must instruct the injured individual to go directly to the local emergency department to be assessed for risk of exposure to blood-borne infection as soon as possible, and preferably within two hours of the incident.
- 4) Service Providers must report any incident relating to a needle stick or eye splash injury to the PIC immediately;
- 5) If the source of blood or bodily fluid is known, Service Providers must ask the individual for their consent to have blood testing done immediately.
- 6) Service Providers must complete the Incident Report Form in the event of a needle stick, eye splash, or any other injury to an individual at the OPS.

28. Handling of Controlled or Unknown Substances

- 1) A Service Provider must not:
 - (a) Provide or transfer a controlled substance to a Service User unless the provision or transfer is for the purposes of drug checking;
 - (b) Take control or possession of a controlled substance for personal use;
 - (c) Take control or possession of a controlled substance for the purpose of transferring the controlled substance for financial compensation, goods, or services; or

- (d) Allow a Service User to leave a controlled substance behind.
- 2) When a controlled or unknown substance is left behind in the OPS, Service Providers must immediately bring it to the attention of the PIC and fill out the Unknown Substances Left Behind form (**Appendix E**).
- 3) Upon discovery of substances left behind, the PIC must immediately:
 - (a) Place the controlled or unknown substance in an envelope;
 - (b) Seal, date, and initial the envelope;
 - (c) Place the envelope in a locked safe;
 - (d) Log the envelope into a record keeping book;
 - (e) Fill out the Unknown Substance Left Behind form (**Appendix E**); and
 - (f) The PIC must ensure that the substances left behind are not accessible to Service Providers or Service Users, except in accordance with these Policies and Procedures.
- 4) Service Providers must not interfere with substances left behind, search sharps containers for substances, or interfere with the storage envelopes containing substances left behind.
- 5) If substances left behind or the storage envelopes containing substances left behind have been lost or interfered with, the PIC must immediately investigate the incident and complete an Incident Report Form.
- 6) At the completion of any investigation pursuant to (6), the PIC has the discretion to report any individual who has interfered with substances left behind, the sharps containers, or the storage envelopes containing substances left behind to the Halifax Regional Police.

29. Harm Reduction and Supplies Distribution

- 1) Service Providers must encourage all Service Users who are there for the purposes of IDU to stay and inject at the OPS.
- 2) If a Service User intends to inject elsewhere, Service Providers must provide needle distribution services regardless of the individual's age, substance using status, or choice of substance.
- 3) Needle distribution services include:
 - (a) Education on the safe disposal of injection equipment;
 - (b) The distribution of adequate injection equipment to enable a safe needle for each injection; and
 - (c) Referrals to Mainline Needle Exchange for larger quantities of equipment.
- 4) If a Service User requires safer smoking services, Service Providers must provide these services regardless of the individual's age, substance using status, choice of substance or whether the Service User intends to use the substance at the OPS.
- 5) Safer smoking services include:
 - (a) The distribution of adequate smoking equipment;
 - (b) Education on safer smoking techniques; and
 - (c) Education on the safe disposal of equipment.
- 6) Service Providers must not provide information to individuals at the OPS on where or how to obtain a controlled substance.

30. Washroom Monitoring

- 1) Service Providers must monitor the washroom use of Service Users to ensure:
 - (a) The safety of Service Users; and
 - (b) That substances are not being used in the washroom.
- 2) Service Providers may access the washroom in case of emergency, even if it is locked from the inside.

31. Sharps Containers

The OPS must only use sharps containers that are made of puncture resistant plastic. Service Providers must ensure that the physical integrity of the sharps containers is not interfered with in any way. The PIC must arrange for the disposal of sharps containers.

32. Safe Cleaning Practices and Disposal of Equipment and Waste

- 1) The OPS must always be kept as clean and tidy as possible.
- 2) To guard against infection and contamination, Service Providers must:
 - (a) Always use a small dustpan and brush to dispose of garbage on a booth;
 - (b) Wear puncture resistant and liquid resistant gloves when cleaning the booths and floors;
 - (c) Ensure that the OPS is well lit; and
 - (d) Wipe down booths, chairs, and mirrors with industrial disinfectant wipes or other hospital grade cleaners
- 3) To ensure that injection equipment is safely disposed of, Service Providers must adhere to the following guidelines:
 - (a) If Service Providers must pick up a needle, they must use tongs or puncture resistant and liquid resistant gloves;
 - (b) Service Providers may only move the sharps containers within the OPS when necessary;
 - (c) Service Providers must ensure that the sharps containers are not filled to more than $\frac{3}{4}$ capacity at any time; and
 - (d) When the sharps containers are at $\frac{3}{4}$ capacity, Service Providers must ensure that they are sealed and taken to Mainline for disposal.
- 4) Guidelines for the disposal of injection equipment and transportation of sharps or waste must be posted in disposal areas and janitorial closets.
- 5) To ensure that the garbage at the OPS is handled safely, Service Providers must:
 - (a) Only handle garbage in the OPS when necessary;
 - (b) Use waterproof garbage bags;
 - (c) Look for injection equipment protruding from garbage bags;
 - (d) Listen for broken glass when moving the bag;
 - (e) Avoid compressing garbage or reaching into the garbage containers;
 - (f) Wear puncture resistant and liquid resistant gloves or use other tools designed for picking up garbage safely;
 - (g) Change bags regularly to prevent overfilling;
 - (h) Hold garbage bags by the top of the bag and away from the body;
 - (i) Avoid placing one hand under the bag to support it;
 - (j) Use tongs or gloves to pick up sharps;
 - (k) Hold needle tips away from the body; and
 - (l) Discard needles in a sharps container.

33. Overdose Response

- 1) In the event of an overdose at the OPS, Service Providers must:
 - (a) Comply with the opioid overdose response training material;
 - (b) Call 911 to request immediate assistance;
 - (c) Notify the PIC;
 - (d) Fill out the Overdose Tracking Sheet (**Appendix I**); and
 - (e) Fill out an Incident Report Form (**Appendix G**).

34. Providing Overdose Assistance Outside of the OPS

- 1) Service Providers may choose to leave the facility to provide services and support if they observe an individual outside of the OPS who requires immediate assistance under the following circumstances:
 - (a) The situation is life threatening and cannot wait until Emergency Health Services arrive;
 - (b) The situation does not present a risk to a Service User's or Service Provider's safety or health; and
 - (c) 911 has been called to request immediate assistance.
- 2) Notwithstanding (1), Service Providers' primary responsibility is to provide service within the OPS, ensure the safety of Service Users and Service Providers on-site, and ensure continuity of services within the OPS. The Service Provider may only respond to an overdose outside of the designated Service Area to provide care if the safety of Service Users and Service Providers inside the OPS is ensured.
- 3) Service Providers must fill out an Incident Report Form if they leave the OPS to provide overdose assistance.

35. Splitting & Sharing Protocol

- 1) Any drug that is used in the OPS/SCS is eligible to be split and/or shared within the site:
 - (a) Splitting and sharing is available to all clients of the OPS/SCS.
 - (b) Splitting and sharing implies the acquisition, separation and/or transfer of a dose between individuals inside the OPS/SCS.
 - (c) The split or share is managed between the individuals engaged in the split/share. Large quantities or exchanges of drugs not intended for personal consumption are out of scope and should not take place within the OPS/SCS.
 - (d) Clients will identify to staff when they intend to engage in a split/share of drugs so that the split or share will occur under the supervision of the OPS/SCS staff.
 - (e) Splitting and/or sharing can occur after admission to the consumption room if required due to different preparation techniques (i.e. if individuals present with pre-prepared drugs in a syringe).
 - (f) The OPS/SCS is for using drugs. Recognizing PWUD are at increased risk of harm related to splitting and sharing outside of an OPS/SCS, one of the individuals engaged in splitting and sharing must be there to consume drugs within the OPS/SCS.
 - (g) No monetary or material trade other than the drugs are allowed in the context of splitting and/or sharing inside the OPS/SCS.
- 2) If there's a joint need for assisted injection with the split dosing, staff should apply both protocols concurrently:
 - (a) Staff welcome the clients/participants who wish to split their dose and try to provide two adjoining (or sharing the same cubicle) cubicles in the injection room.
 - (b) Preparing the dose:
 - i. Sharing a liquid substance: the dose is split from a recipient or via the injection material once the dose has been prepared.
 - ii. Sharing a dry substance: the dose is split before preparing the injection. Staff may provide a scale if available on site. Clients may decide whether to split the dose dry, or to prepare it and split once it is in solution/liquid form.
 - iii. If passing a syringe to another participant, request participants to cap the syringe prior to passing.

36. Death Protocol

- 1) Upon a death of an individual in the Service Area, a Service Provider must:
 - (a) Call 911 to request immediate assistance;
 - (b) Secure the immediate area around the individual and prohibit access to the area to other Service Users;
 - (c) Advise the RPIC immediately;
 - (d) Fill out an Incident Report Form; and
 - (e) Cooperate with any subsequent investigations.

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